

DiSSCo Transition Project

Wrap-up Event

Work Package 5 - Deliverable 5.3

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DiSSCo Transition Project
Wrap-up event - April 1st 2025

List of abbreviations

CETAF - Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities

CMS - Collections Management System

CSRD - Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DiSSCover - DiSSCo's Unified Curation and Annotation System

DOI - Digital Object Identifier

DSArch - Digital Specimen Architecture

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

ELViS - European Loans and Visits System

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud

ERIC - European Research Infrastructure Consortium

ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

EU - European Union

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

FAQ(s) - Frequently Asked Question(s)

GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility

GRSciColl - Global Registry of Scientific Collections

IRL - Implementation Readiness Level

LtC - Latimer Core

MAS(s) - Machine Annotation Service(s)

MIDS - Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen

NN(s) - DiSSCo National Node(s)

openDS - open Digital Specimen

PID - Persistent Identifier

RI - Research Infrastructure

TCS2 - Taxon Concept Standard version 2

TDWG - Biodiversity Information Standards

TRL - Technology Readiness Level

WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

This document reports on the DiSSCo Transition Project (DTP)'s Wrap-Up Event (deliverable 5.3), which took place on April 1, 2025, hosted by Naturalis (Coordinator) at its premises in Leiden. It consists of a compendium of the sessions that took place during the event.

The objective of the event was to wrap up the DiSSCo Transition Project, which started on the 1st of December 2023, by:

- Presenting the work package developments in line with the work plan while preparing the project's closing (31 May 2025);
- Showcasing the project results' impact and value for the future operation of DiSSCo ERIC and the community; and
- Providing recommendations on:
 - The focus for next year until DiSSCo ERIC is established (foreseen in 2026), and
 - On a longer-term basis, what DiSSCo ERIC should first look into from a work package perspective as the beacon of expertise in the respective theme –standards, infrastructure, policy, business, and community.

The event comprised several consecutive sessions, as well as a [roundtable](#) with five DiSSCo National Nodes representatives, moderated by CETAF (see section 3.3 of this document).

Furthermore, the event was integrated into a [series of DiSSCo events](#), being followed by the 7th DiSSCo interim General Assembly Meeting and the DiSSCo 2nd Interim Council Meeting.

2. Key facts of the event

Deliverable 5.3, led by Naturalis (WP5), was achieved in time.

DTP and the wider DiSSCo community were well represented at the meeting, with 37 attendants representing multiple facilities and strategic partners.

Gender distribution

The event was [opened](#) by the Project Coordinator and DiSSCo RI Executive Director, Dimitris Koureas, who reminded the audience of the path that brought DiSSCo RI to its current Transition phase. DiSSCo RI entered the ESFRI roadmap in 2018 and successfully concluded its Preparatory phase in early 2023. The RI is now transitioning towards the constitution of its legal entity, an ERIC, and the start of its scaled-up construction (implementation) programme.

The Transition phase is underpinned by the [DiSSCo Transition Project](#), a project that brings together 16 Partners with the primary goal of ensuring the seamless transition of the DiSSCo RI from its Preparatory phase to the Construction phase (expected to start in 2026).

3. Sessions in the spotlight

3.1. Business dimension

This session started with the [presentation of WP1 by its leader](#), Eva Alonso, Head of Governance of DiSSCo RI.

WP1 contributed to the project's objective of advancing the organisational readiness of the future DiSSCo ERIC and completing its policy framework, ensuring the smooth early-phase Implementation of DiSSCo.

Indeed, Step 1 of the ERIC application was submitted at the end of February 2025, which is a significant milestone representing the perseverance and commitment of all involved after several years of work with key stakeholders, notably funding agencies, towards bringing forward the wealth of collections to the world of accelerated knowledge for nature.

Other outputs of this work package include the data and access policies, the procurement and financial frameworks, and the employment and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) policies.

These policies will support the maturity of DiSSCo ERIC by fostering alignment at multiple levels (e.g. institutional, EOSC), ensuring interoperability, access coordination, data protection, and benefits deriving from economies of scale. Its uptake was highlighted as a recommended focus point in the long run.

WP1 has also invested in developing the socio-economic impact assessment framework for DiSSCo, which will highlight the added value of the pan-European research infrastructure for different groups of stakeholders in the key areas of research, economy, society, and policy. The next step will be to develop its implementation plan, for which the engagement of the National Nodes and strategic partners will be necessary.

As next steps towards the Step 2 submission, WP1 highlighted the need to continue supporting the DiSSCo governing bodies, the interim General Assembly and the Interim Council. On a longer-term perspective, strengthening the advocacy strategy towards the expansion of the ERIC membership was underlined, for which communication and closely following the evolution of national priorities are key. With regards to DiSSCo services, it is advised to establish trust-based relationships with users and to promote involvement with sister initiatives, including beyond the biodiversity domain.

Next, WP2 leader, Ana Casino, the Executive Director of the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF), and DiSSCo RI Deputy Coordinator, delivered this work package's presentation.

WP2's objective revolved around engaging and supporting DiSSCo National Nodes in strengthening national commitments. For this, WP2 has been ensuring a regular communication flow, fostering consultation on critical aspects (e.g. the Scientific and Technical Description of DiSSCo) and delivering updates on main developments while collecting and disseminating information on lessons learnt to channel effective participation and operation.

For this, WP2 moderated monthly meetings and co-organised workshops. This contributed to participation and engagement, tackling the different Implementation Readiness Level (IRL) dimensions of DiSSCo, including the technical dimension. The work entailed detecting user needs and assessing user awareness, providing the basis for the first layer of support of the DiSSCo Helpdesk.

Furthermore, WP2 contributed to fostering inclusion and commitment through the provision of data with the Specialisation tool, thus demonstrating the value and efficiency of a comprehensive and harmonised mechanism to gather data, including for DiSSCo services, in alignment with main data aggregating services (CETAF Registry of Collections, GRSciColl [Global Registry of Scientific Collections] and ELViS [European Loans and Visits System]).

All of these efforts have contributed to building up the sense of community, supporting the current and future National Nodes in seamlessly transitioning towards becoming fully operational Nodes of the DiSSCo RI. As such, major recommendations from WP2 resided in

preventing the loss of commitment and engagement of National Nodes whose countries are not members of the ERIC, and avoiding lowering the interaction with facilities. At the same time, it was recommended to exploit the results of the implementation of the core services to facilitate the adhesion of new facilities and the participation of new countries. The Nodes Committee, within the framework of DiSSCo ERIC's governance, will have a critical role in advancing engagement and participation. When in full operation, DiSSCo ERIC will benefit from investing in providing training to facilities on the use/operation of the core services provided by DiSSCo ERIC.

3.2. Technical dimension

This session was initiated by WP3, with a [presentation by Claus Weiland](#), from the Senckenberg Digital Collection Technologies (SDCT), leader of the work package.

WP3 centred itself on advancing the development of core e-services to avoid the accumulation of technical debt before the start of the Implementation phase of DiSSCo RI. For this, WP3 focused on establishing a minimum viable product of core infrastructure, integrating key e-services (e.g. ELViS), and updating the data management plan for DiSSCo RI, including machine actionability.

In terms of the impact of the results achieved, this encompassed significant improvements in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the Digital Specimen Architecture (DSArch), achieved with the use of real-world quality data, progress in integration of the data model and services, minting PIDs for Digital Specimen in high throughput and at scale, bulk-indexing of digital media objects, and a self-hosted service based on Keycloak for authentication and authorisation.

It is worth noting the achievements regarding Machine Annotation Services (MASs), integrated into [DiSSCover](#), DiSSCo's platform for curating and annotating digital specimens, which serve as digital surrogates for physical specimens. DiSSCover provides access to all specimen-related data, including metadata, digital media and derived or related data like sequence data, chemical composition and sampled environment. Users, including researchers, taxonomic experts and citizen scientists, can annotate and enrich specimen data to support science, with future integration of approved annotations pending a community review process. The MASs are automated services that annotate a target in DiSSCo. These services are scheduled by users for individual specimens or media in DiSSCo.

As more immediate next steps in the path towards DiSSCo ERIC, WP3 highlighted:

- Developing onboarding procedures, and onboarding first collection-derived data and MASs;
- Addressing end-user demands;
- Preparing negotiations with identified potential core service providers;
- Further developing ELViS towards an MVP and multi-institutional capabilities;
- Promoting the adoption of DOIs as essential added-value services.

In the longer term, the identified priorities were:

- Establishing a good inventory of the collections (e.g. species level estimations) to improve access and support digitisation and management plans;
- Promoting large-scale (low-res) imaging and MASs to speed up digitisation;
- Developing a roadmap towards having digital specimen DOIs for all specimens in the world;
- Developing national infrastructures for digital media to support AI model training;
- Developing the scientific and technological unique features: traceability back to the physical specimen enables the integration of resampling and re-measuring of the specific physical object into the research process.

The session was closed with a presentation by WP4 leader Laurence Livermore, Digital Programme Manager at the Natural History Museum in London.

WP4 occupied itself with continuing international collaboration on standards and best practices needed for the DiSSCo service provision. In particular, WP4 aimed at i) reporting on the state of standards interoperability and undertaking a gap analysis for the next stage of DiSSCo RI development, supporting continued development and adoption of new community standards; and ii) writing and evaluating documentation for DiSSCo's operational services and related standards, and report the use of pilot DiSSCo infrastructure and the adoption of contemporary practices following workshops and community consultation.

The impact of the work in WP4 has resulted in:

- Enhanced Standards for Biodiversity Data ([Latimer Core](#), [openDS](#), [MIDS](#), [TCS2](#)):
 - [Latimer Core](#) (LtC) passed its formal review and ratification in early 2024;
 - The open Digital Specimen standard (openDS) underwent and completed a public review in late 2024;
 - Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen (MIDS) has started its formal review process to achieve ratification;
 - Taxon Concept Standard version 2 (TCS2) is nearing its public review.
- Promotion and Awareness of Standards (workshops, documentation): WP4 presented on and ran workshops for LtC and TCS2 combined with the [DiSSCo Data Management Plan for machine actionability](#), collecting feedback from prospective users, helping them understand use cases and relevance, and improving documentation and training material for the standards.
- Strengthened Future Biodiversity Data Infrastructure (adoption, interoperability): The infrastructure was strengthened by getting standards like LtC adopted by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)'s collections registry, GRSciColl, writing a DiSSCo EU LtC profile, and planning implementation in collections management systems, ensuring wider adoption and future interoperability.

As next steps until the constitution of DiSSCo ERIC, WP4 provided the following recommendations:

- Continue to support and participate in the MIDS ratification process and its subsequent uptake and implementation across DiSSCo's distributed technical teams and systems:
 - Actively engage with the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) community and other relevant organisations to ensure MIDS reaches full ratification.
 - Provide technical and administrative support for the finalisation of the MIDS standard.
 - Facilitate internal adoption within DiSSCo, ensuring that all relevant systems, tools, and services integrate MIDS as part of their data workflows.
 - Conduct training sessions and produce onboarding materials for technical teams to assist with implementation.
 - Monitor and document challenges, feedback, and solutions from early implementers to refine the adoption strategy.
- Work with key groups involved in biodiversity aggregation and standards development to promote adoption and alignment of standards:
 - Strengthen collaboration between data aggregators and providers to ensure consistency and interoperability between different biodiversity data infrastructures.
 - Actively contribute to standards development discussions to ensure DiSSCo's needs are represented in ongoing refinements of biodiversity standards.
 - Develop a targeted outreach plan to encourage widespread adoption among institutions, collections, and data providers.
 - Organise joint workshops and technical meetings to facilitate knowledge exchange and alignment of implementation strategies.
- Improve documentation for how DiSSCo is implementing key standards for its infrastructure, aimed at a mixed audience of users, implementers, and national nodes:
 - Develop clear, accessible documentation covering i) technical specifications for implementing standards in DiSSCo systems; ii) step-by-step guides for collections managers and researchers on integrating their data with DiSSCo; iii) best practices and FAQs tailored to national nodes and other stakeholders; iv) ensure documentation is available in multiple formats, including written guides, interactive tutorials, and video walkthroughs; and v) maintain an iterative approach, gathering user feedback and refining documentation to address common challenges and needs.
- Identify and document scientific and community use cases that demonstrate the value of new and emerging standards:
 - Work with researchers, collection managers, and biodiversity data users to identify real-world applications of new standards.
 - Develop case studies showcasing how MIDS, LtC, and openDS improve data interoperability, accessibility, and reuse.

- Highlight examples where FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) lead to better research outcomes.
- Use insights from these case studies to inform further refinements of DiSSCo's infrastructure and guide future community engagement efforts.
- Share findings through conference presentations, publications, and workshops to demonstrate impact and encourage broader adoption.

For the longer term, WP4 underscored:

- Incentivise the use of Latimer Core within the DiSSCo EU community for the discovery of collections and facilities:
 - Develop clear benefits and use cases demonstrating how Latimer Core enhances collection visibility and accessibility.
 - Collaborate with DiSSCo National Nodes and institutional partners to integrate Latimer Core into discovery platforms and portals.
 - Establish pilot projects with key institutions to showcase the advantages of Latimer Core in metadata enrichment and collection discovery.
 - Provide technical and financial support where possible (e.g., funding small-scale adoption projects or offering development assistance).
 - Recognise early adopters through community spotlights, case studies, and conference presentations to build momentum.
- Encourage the implementation of emerging standards in collections management and associated institutional systems:
 - Work with collections management system (CMS) providers to ensure compatibility with emerging standards, including openDS, Latimer Core, and MIDS.
 - Develop a certification or endorsement programme for CMS platforms that align with DiSSCo's data standards.
 - Provide technical resources and implementation guidelines to help institutions integrate new standards with minimal disruption.
 - Organise stakeholder forums and working groups to address institutional challenges and share best practices for implementation.
 - Partner with funding agencies to advocate for financial support for collections that implement and maintain compliance with these standards.
- Demonstrate successful adoption of DiSSCo's technical services based on new standards (openDS, Latimer Core, and MIDS):
 - Create a repository of case studies showcasing how DiSSCo's technical services improve data interoperability, research efficiency, and collection discoverability.
 - Partner with research institutions, museums, and natural history collections to document successful real-world applications of these standards.
 - Develop impact metrics to assess adoption rates, interoperability improvements, and user satisfaction with DiSSCo's services.
 - Support pilot research projects using DiSSCo's services to demonstrate their effectiveness and encourage further uptake.

- Present findings at international conferences, biodiversity informatics workshops, and policy forums to promote awareness and credibility.
- Support ongoing international community engagement and training with standards, including geo-collections:
 - Establish a long-term training program that includes workshops, webinars, and online courses on biodiversity data standards.
 - Build a global network of expert trainers to support institutions in implementing and using new standards.
 - Expand collaborations with geo-collections communities to ensure integration within DiSSCo's infrastructure.
 - Develop multilingual training materials to support adoption across diverse regions.
 - Maintain active participation in international biodiversity data forums to align DiSSCo's work with broader global efforts.
- Track and measure real-world applications and scientific impact:
 - Establish tracking mechanisms to measure the ongoing impact of standards adoption on research and data sharing.
 - Use quantitative and qualitative methods to assess interoperability improvements, research citations, and institutional adoption.
 - Engage with policy-makers and funding bodies to ensure that DiSSCo's impact informs future investments in biodiversity informatics.

3.3. Roundtable with DiSSCo National Nodes

The National Nodes community is instrumental in supporting the RI's constituency, operation and sustainability, for which the endorsement of the DiSSCo principles by the vast range of researchers, the implementation of consistent and interoperable procedures by the facilities involved, and an overarching vision of how to run and sustain the RI shared at the European level are needed.

Therefore, this session focused on i) bringing forward what makes an NN unique, elaborating on the specificities of an NN that might differ from the others; ii) moving on to the Construction phase, identifying crucial components that need to be addressed in preparation for joining DiSSCo ERIC, taking into consideration the Technical, Organisational, Financial, Data and Scientific dimensions.

The session was moderated by Ana Casino (CETAF, WP2 leader). The panel included five DiSSCo National Nodes representatives:

- Belgium - Serge Scory, Business and Research Development Manager, Research Office General Direction, at the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS).
- United Kingdom - Alan Paton, Head of Science Collections Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.
- Denmark - Kim Steenstrup Pedersen, Image Section - Department of Computer Science (DIKU) | Head of Section for Digital Collections & Archives, at the Natural History Museum of Denmark (NHMD) - University of Copenhagen.

- France - François Dusoulier, Head of Collections Research Infrastructure | Coordinator of the National Network of Naturalist Collections | Head Curator, at the National Museum of Natural History (MNHN) in Paris.
- The Netherlands - Niels Raes, Programme Manager Biodiversity Informatics at Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

The European scientific facilities across Europe are very diverse in typology, size, funding, governance structures, and even in the development status of their digitisation efforts. Therefore, the National Nodes are also different in size, representation, commitment, and linkage to the funding of national agencies. Regarding the NN in the panel:

- BE: A node that needs to integrate different governmental instances.
- UK: A node that gathers a plurality of institutions.
- DK: A node that benefits from continued national funding support over the years.
- FR: A node where one institution has the mandate to coordinate the others at national level.
- NL: A node in a country that will host DiSSCo ERIC.

During the DTP, special efforts were dedicated to supporting the National Nodes, including the development of a common narrative to transmit to their national authorities, towards consolidating participation in DiSSCo ERIC.

From the discussions during the roundtable, it is worth highlighting:

- Constraints:
 - Facilities' fear of the unknown;
 - Lack of awareness of existing resources;
 - Fewer resources and isolation of smaller facilities.

Improving the network/ diversity will help solve this type of issues, for instance, promoting inclusion of smaller collection-holding institutes, considering special thematics, hubs, etc.
By the same token, more institutions taking part in governance will result in more diversity, thus influencing buy-in.
More distribution of costs will require visibility of [immediate] benefits.
- Challenge:
 - Secure funding for continued digitisation and for participation in DiSSCo ERIC.
- Benefits for the governments: Citations, connecting the science institutions, the value of the community, and economies of scale.
- Exploring private funding:
 - The [Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive](#) (CSRD) mandates that impact is reported. Nature-positive organisations should be frontrunners in showing their solutions.

Potential challenge about private funding: ambivalent effects of open access—either the private sector limits open access for their own data and avoids nonexclusivity, or they adopt the stance ‘Prove me that I need you’ as they already have access to significant data and metadata to develop their products. However, expertise (e.g., taxonomists) to work with the data is key. At the same time, it needs to be demanded that the private actors are respectful of where the data came from.

- Common vision:
 - It is critical to have a common vision about digitisation. The value of the collections can be proved; their use must be maximised.
- Momentum:
 - It is important to keep the momentum with the monthly NN meetings. The ‘not-so-successful’ stories should also be shared, so that others can anticipate and prepare for potential similar obstacles.

4. Conclusion

DiSSCo is Europe’s flagship research infrastructure for natural science collections, bringing together hundreds of museums, botanical gardens, universities, and other collection-holding institutions across 23 countries. DiSSCo digitally unifies, harmonises and makes accessible European natural science assets. By providing a unified access point to Europe’s natural science collections, DiSSCo enables data-driven research addressing biodiversity, climate change, health, and food security, directly supporting Horizon Europe Missions and the European Green Deal.

Moreover, DiSSCo exemplifies open science by making research outputs openly accessible and reusable, in line with EU mandates for FAIR and open data sharing. The infrastructure supports new metrics for research impact and integrity, reinforcing the reproducibility and transparency of EU-funded science.

This document presented the DiSSCo Transition Project Wrap-Up Event’s major outcomes, during which it was demonstrated that the project enabled substantial progress in unifying Europe’s natural science collections, advancing open science, and supporting EU policy objectives. Sustained investment in DiSSCo will be vital to fulfil its mission and its capacity to address pressing societal challenges.

5. Presentations

DiSSCo Ri

TRANSITION

DiSSCo Transition Project
Wrap-up event - April 1st 2025

Agenda

12:00-13:30	Registration / Lunch			
1	13:30-13:50	Welcome by the Coordinator	Dimitris Koureas	Naturalis Auditorium
2	13:50-14:35	Business dimension - achievements	WP1, WP2	
14:35-14:40	Group picture			
14:40-15:10	Coffee break [Auditorium's Foyer]			
3	15:10-15:55	Technical dimension - achievements	WP3, WP4	Naturalis Auditorium
4	15:55-16:05	Closing of the project	Vânia Ferreira (WP5)	
5	16:05-17:00	Round table with DiSSCo National Nodes	Ana Casino	
6	17:00-17:30	Next steps and closing of the meeting	Dimitris Koureas	
17:30-20:00	Reception [Auditorium's Foyer]			

Welcome by the Coordinator

Dimitris Koureas

DTP: Getting through the finishing line

DiSSCo Timeline

DiSSCo Prepare

- Improve implementation readiness level

DiSSCo Transition

- Engagement
- Continuity
- Consolidation

DiSSCo ERIC

- Construction

Implementation Readiness Levels of DiSSCo

Implementation Readiness Level

Areas of work (WPs)

WP1: ERIC Roadmap and Policy Framework

WP2: National Nodes Engagement and Inclusion

WP3: Data Infrastructure and Core Services

WP4: International Collaboration on (Data) Standards

WP5: Management, Communication and Outreach

Consortium Partnership

Naturalis Biodiversity Center
Netherlands

Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF)
Belgium

Senckenberg Society for Nature Research
Germany

Meise Botanic Garden
Belgium

X-Officio Advokat AB
Sweden

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
Belgium

Natural History Museum London
United Kingdom

University of Crete
Greece

University of Lisbon
Portugal

University of Copenhagen
Denmark

University of Florence
Italy

Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle

Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Bulgaria

Plant Science and Biodiversity Centre, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Institute of Botany
Slovak Republic

University of Tartu
Estonia

Free University Berlin
Germany

Business dimension achievements

WP1, WP2

Eva M. Alonso (Naturalis Biodiversity Center) - WP1
Ana Casino (CETAF) - WP2

Business dimension WPI - Organisational Readiness

Brief introduction

Goal: Pave the way towards the ERIC - application process & operations

Starting point: CMP recommendations

Outputs:

1. **Application process** - Step 1 submitted in Feb 2025 (Naturalis)
2. **Operations**
 - a. *4 Implementing rules* - GA RoP; EB ToR; NC RoP; SETAB RoP (X-Officio)
 - b. *5 Policies* - Data; Access; IPRs; Employment & Procurement (RBINS, MeiseBG)
 - c. Financial Framework & service cost alternatives (MNHN)
3. **DiSSCo added-value**
 - a. Socio-economic Impact Assessment Framework (SEIF) (Naturalis)

Business dimension WPI - Organisational Readiness

WPI overall impact on ERIC's operation

- Provide early in time key components for organisational, scientific and technical **DiSSCo maturity**, allowing fast transition towards full operation
- **Consolidate a way of working together** - Stakeholders engagement
 - For an efficient approval & implementation
 - To guarantee quality
 - To build trust in community and strategic partners
- Building future DiSSCo-case around impact on society
 - **Long-term sustainability**

Business dimension WP1 - Organisational Readiness

How does the Policy Framework support the maturity of DiSSCo ERIC?

Data Policy	Access Policy
Centralised data governance framework	Centralised governance for coordination of access
Identified technical and organisational structures	Predefined standardised access and service management structure
Secure and reliable data storage	Federated Authentication and Authorisation
Open access protecting sensitive data	Access monitoring and reporting system
Alignment with EOSC principles & existing institutional policies	Immediate interoperability with existing institutional policies
Regular policy review and compliance monitoring	

Business dimension WPI - Organisational Readiness

How does the Policy Framework support the maturity of DiSSCo ERIC?

Procurement Policy

Identified preferred governance structure

Centralised yet collaborative process to enable operational stability

Pro active design of secure and reliable purchase processes

Support innovation at national, regional and EU level

Centralised legal expertise to ensure alignment with EU regulations and existing institutional procedures

Supports the generation of benefits from economies of scale and promotes consistent ethical behaviours

Business dimension WPI/CSO - Organisational Readiness

Next steps until the constitution of DiSSCo ERIC

- Application process - Step 2 submission
 - Support DiSSCo Interim Council
 - Advocacy strategy (funders/nodes)
 - Final documentation prep.
- Operations - Actions “between steps”
 - Finalisation of WPI outputs (Employment & IPRs)
 - New communication narrative (s)
 - Encourage NNs to communicate internally
 - SEIF implementation plan

Organisational Readiness

(Longer-term) Recommendations for DiSSCo ERIC (cfr. CMP)

- Strength advocacy strategy tow. ERIC membership expansion
- Establish long-term, trust-based relationship betw. users & DiSSCo services
- Reinforce communication and communication tools at national level
- Encourage use of self-assessment tools and policies uptake
- Set up a KPI plan and a risk assessment plan in Y1
- Engage nodes and strategic partners in annual performance & impact assessments

Organisational Readiness

(Longer-term) Recommendations for DiSSCo ERIC (cfr. CMP)

- Empower nodes to continue building DiSSCo
- Encourage alignment with sister initiatives, also beyond the biodiversity domain
- Prioritise the alignment with national priorities
- Set up agile, transparent decision-making processes
- Engagement of stakeholders established as *modus operandi*

Business dimension WP2

WP2 – Engagement and Inclusion

As a distributed RI, DiSSCo relies on and serves the **facilities** that constitute its building blocks, gathered around National Nodes to organise participation at national level.

National Nodes are a **fundamental actor** in the development and the future operation of the RI.

For that, contributions are the result of the work carried out in three different tasks:

- Engagement (developed under Task T2.1)
- Inclusion and commitment (sought via Task T2.2)
- Support (structured in Task T2.3)

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.1-Consolidate channels of participation of NNs in the development of DiSSCo

WP2, specifically through Task T2.1, has facilitated the participation of the National Nodes and consolidated **Engagement** through:

- **Keeping a regular communication flow**
 - Consultation on critical aspects and updates on main developments
 - Feedback on status quo in different DiSSCo Nodes
- **Developing a participatory schema (D2.1)**
 - To collect main findings
 - To highlight success stories, with lessons learned for others
 - To convey certain recommendations towards effective operation

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.1-Consolidate channels of participation of NNs in the development of DiSSCo

1. Regular monthly meetings

- The **specialisation plan** (to institutional and collections data)
- Refinement of the **Scientific & Technical Description** (specifically in relation to the definition of the service provision)
- **Helpdesk** (Survey 1st layer of the Helpdesk for the different core services)
- **Workshops:**
 - With WP3 (30 October'24): Core **technical infrastructure** and the Minimum Viable Products)
 - With WP1 (31 October'24): **Data policy** framework
 - With WP4: conclusions from webinars and workshops around **standards**
 - ✓ TDWG-SPNHC (2-6 October'24): NHM- User and technical stakeholder workshop on standards
 - ✓ 21-22 January'25: UTARTU- DiSSCo DMP and Standards for Taxon Hypotheses

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.1-Consolidate channels of participation of NNs in the development of DiSSCo

2. Outline for the participatory schema for National Nodes (D2.1) - M18

The Schema aims to **capture the main aspects** relevant for the Nodes' participation in DiSSCo ERIC and to **ensure a smooth progress** until the establishment of the legal entity and its full operation:

- **Organisation** of the Node (internal formation and expansion, participation in the governance of the ERIC, etc.)
- **Integration** of the Node in the RI (data policies, interoperability, standardisation)
- **Functional** funding (securing financial support on the national level)
- **Operation** of services (service provision and use)

The document will be based on the latest **findings** on the different dimensions of DiSSCo and it will draw upon the five **NN reports** delivered during DTP (SK, IT, DE, BG and DK).

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.1-Consolidate channels of participation of NNs in the development of DiSSCo

Achievements:

- Consolidate engagement at national level
- Procure a sustained open forum of discussion for NNs
- Deliver a set of recommendations (a “schema”) to support the current and future National Nodes in seamlessly transitioning from the current stage towards to becoming fully integrated Nodes of the DiSSCo RI

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.2 - Identify means to sustainably collect, aggregate and analyse information

Task T2.2 has been dedicated to foster **inclusion and commitment** from the Nodes (and the facilities at national level) through the provision of data to demonstrate the value and efficiency of a comprehensive and harmonised mechanism to gather data, with the Specialisation tool.

The **Specialisation tool** is one of the main practical outcomes of WP2:

- Institutions and Collections data
- Alignment with CETAF Registry, ELViS and GRSciColl
- Integration of standards
- Combination of GeoCase for geological collections

We have run webinars, presentations during NNs meetings and have a regular exchange of information to facilitate provision of data.

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.2 - Identify means to sustainably collect, aggregate and analyse information

Integration and adoption roadmap of assessment tools (D2.2) - M18

An authoritative data source for:

- Collecting high-level **institutional data** (including collection scope and size, digitisation capacity, facilities, organisational structure, research expertise, and training programs)
- Providing data to **DiSSCo services**, such as ELViS and the Collection Digitisation Dashboard.
- Providing a user-friendly **interface for viewing and analysing data**, that will be integrated into the CETAF website to support strategic decision making, including identifying Centers of Excellence (CoEs), facilitating research collaborations, supporting policy development and national/international strategic management

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.2 - Identify means to sustainably collect, aggregate and analyse information

no plus the content area

CETAF/DiSSCo specialisation

by marsadmin — last modified Mar 12, 2024 11:50 AM

Choose one of the topic to access the menu

Institution	Collections	Research	Expertise	Trainings	Museum	Facilities

1.

You are here: Home / CETAF Passport and Collections registry input

CETAF/DISSCo specialisation

by marsadmin — last modified Mar 12, 2024 11:00 AM

Choose one of the topic to access the menu

Institution

Collections

Research

Expertise

Trainings

2.

Google Forms and XLS files

5.

Institution

The purpose of this form is for CETAF and/or DISSCo members to provide data on their institution's administrative and organisational aspects. The data will be uploaded to the CETAF registry and will be aggregated by DISSCo.

This form requires a valid google account to upload extra files. You can use your personal account or create a new one for this purpose. The email address will be your contact email to modify your data in the future.

sspwdp.rbins@gmail.com [Switch accounts](#)

The name and photo associated with your Google Account will be recorded when you upload files and submit this form. Only the email address you enter is part of your response.

* Indicates required question

Email *

patrick.semal@naturalsciences.be

Contact person ORCID-ID *

ORCID-ID of the contact person who filled this form, e.g. 0000-0002-4048-7728. The public information of the ORCID portal will be reused avoiding multiple encoding.

0000-0002-4048-7728

3.

Elastic Search Index

elasticsearch

4.

Distributed System of Scientific Collections

4.

1.

CETAF
COMMITTEE OF EUROPEAN TAXONOMY FACILITIES

DISCO
Distributed System of Scientific Collections

You are here: Home / CETAF Passport and Collections registry Input

CETAF/DISCO specialisation
by marsadmin — last modified Mar '12, 2024 11:50 AM

Choose one of the topic to access the menu

- Institution
- Collections
- Research
- Expertise
- Trainings

2.

Google Forms and XLS files

Validated forms and sheets

Institution

The purpose of this form is for CETAF and/or DISCO members to provide data on their institution's administrative and organisational aspects. The data will be uploaded to the

Validation + prefilled forms and sheets

* Indicates required question

Email *

patrick.semal@naturalsciences.be

Contact person ORCID-ID *

ORCID-ID of the contact person who filled this form, e.g. 0000-0002-4048-7728. The public information of the ORCID portal will be reused avoiding multiple encoding.

0000-0002-4048-7728

5.

3. Updated infos

PostgreSQL + **django**

DISCO
Distributed System of Scientific Collections

ELViS

4.

Latimer Core

GBIF
Global Biodiversity Information Facility

5. **Global Registry of Scientific Collections**

4. A worldwide catalogue of scientific collections

Institution name	Digitized specimens ∞
Search institutions	🔍

4.

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.2 - Identify means to sustainably collect, aggregate and analyse information

Achievements:

- Specialisation tool fully defined and deployed for institutional access
- 67 Institutions and 33 collections have fully implemented the forms
- Alignment with main data aggregating services (CETAF Registry of Collections, GRSciColl and ELViS)

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.3 - Provide entry-point resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk

WP2 has prepared means of **support** (T2.3) to the Nodes by delivering the model for the first layer of the DiSSCo Helpdesk, a crucial line of support for future users of the RI.

The work entailed carrying out a survey among the Nodes to detect **user needs and assess user awareness** of key DiSSCo service, as well as identify preferred **support format** in relation to each service. The survey results, once analysed and processed, provided the basis for visualising the first layer of support and providing recommendations for each of the included services:

- ELViS
- Collection Digitisation Dashboard
- Digital Specimen Repository
- DiSSCover

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.3 - Provide entry-point resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk

Integration and adoption roadmap of assessment tools (D2.2) - M16

The report outlines a structured model for developing self-service resources as the first layer of support within the DiSSCo Helpdesk. Recommendations include

- **structuring** support resources based on user roles,
- **centralising** materials on dedicated help pages, and
- **ensuring** ongoing updates through collaboration between service providers and the helpdesk.

By implementing these strategies, the DiSSCo Helpdesk aims to improve user experience, streamline support services, and ensure researchers, collection managers, policymakers, and citizen scientists can effectively utilize DiSSCo's distributed services.

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.3 - Provide entry-point resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk

Self-resourced Helpdesk - Workflow between the Helpdesk and DiSSCo Services

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

T2.3 - Provide entry-point resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk

Achievements:

- **Deployment of 1st layer of helping / support resources**
- **Linkage to users needs**
- **Alignment with DiSSCo Services (and its future integration through the SLAs)**

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

Impact and usefulness

The main **impacts** created through WP2 that underpin the usefulness of the tools created in WP2:

- Sense of united **community**
- Recurrent **interaction** with facilities (data providers and services' users)
- Conveying **messages** to foster participation at national level
- Advancement in providing **supporting tools** to even and balance participation across countries
- Provision of **clear and updated information** on the technical progress and the means to translate those within facilities

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

1010
1010

Challenges in the process towards DiSSCo ERIC

The following aspects are identified as the main **risks and challenges**:

- Losing the commitment and engagement of national nodes which countries are not members of the ERIC
- Focusing exclusively on active Nodes
- Lowering interaction with facilities

These challenges need to be seen as **opportunities** and for that:

- Use the scientific **community** gathered around CETAF to keep engagement
- Make a substantial effort on **dissemination and awareness** for the specialisation tool population
- Provide recurrent **training**
- Largely **exploit the results** of the implementation of the core services to facilitate adherence of new facilities and participation of new countries

Business dimension WP2-NNs Engagement and Inclusion

Recommendations for DiSSCo ERIC

For **governance**:

- Critical to keep **engagement and participation**
- Fundamental to operationalise the **governing bodies** to channel the participation of National Nodes through the Nodes Committee
- Important to provide **advise** considering national priorities and needs

For **full operation**:

- Encourage active **participation** of the NNs in all steps of the process, as users of services and providers of information
- Ensure **training** to facilities on the use/operation of the core services provided by DiSSCo ERIC
- Support use of **means and tools** to implement efficiently the necessary data-sharing to populate the Specialisation tool and exploit the results through the Dashboard
- **Configure** the helpdesk as a support service to the operation of the RI

Technical dimension achievements

WP3, WP4

Claus Weiland (Senckenberg)
Wouter Addink (Naturalis)
Laurence Livermore (NHM London)

Technical dimension WP3

Objectives - Data Infrastructure and Core Services

- **Advance DiSSCo's data infrastructure to a minimum viable product** in preparation for operation under the ERIC and adapt to evolving data standards (T3.1)
- **Integrate key e-services** with the DiSSCo data infrastructure and improve technical readiness (T3.2)
- **Update the DiSSCo Data Management Plan** in preparation for operation under the ERIC and **advance the DMP in support of machine-actionability** (T3.3)

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

Impact and results achieved → DS arch (3.1)

Significant improvements were made with all components underlining the advancement from proof of concept (TRL 4-5) to the demonstration of technological applicability with real-world data (TRL 6):

- Digital Specimen Repository → **substantial progress of the integration of datamodel** ([openDS 0.4.0](#), [FDO profiles 1.0](#)) **and data quality + completeness checks** ([MIDS→DwC SSSOM](#)) into DSarch
- Persistent Identifier Infrastructure → **established interplay with Datacite** to mint PIDs for Digital Specimen (DOIs) in high throughput and at scale
- Data processing and publishing → **improved MAS batch processing and MAS provider integration**
- Indexing and API → **bulk indexing of digital media objects** including detection of doublettes
- Authorisation and Authentication infrastructure (AAI) → **migration** from the previous service provider GRNET **to self-hosted solution based on Keycloak**

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

Impact and results achieved → e-Service ecosystem (3.2)

- Core objective: **Build DiSSCo's ecosystem of distributed services** focussing on **Loan and visits (ELViS)**, **summary on progress and quality (MIDS)** of the digitization of **collections (CDD)**, and adding **annotations** (assigning of context and extraction of features) **to Digital Specimen or associated media objects (MAS)**
- **CDD: Developed plan for integration in DS arch** based on assessment of current implementations at DiSSCo UK and DiSSCo Flanders (MS3.2)

Technical dimension WP3

Impact and results achieved → ELViS impressions

- Environment (pre-production) **managed by MNHN on base of MUSE**
- pre-production version of ELViS running at elvis.dissco.eu **following DiSSCo's graphic scheme**
- **Using Digital Specimens** from DS arch (API)

The screenshot shows the ELViS (EUROPEAN LOANS AND VISITS SYSTEM) interface. At the top left is the logo 'ELViS EUROPEAN LOANS AND VISITS SYSTEM'. At the top right are navigation links: 'HOME MY PROJECTS MY ACCOUNT | EN'. The main content area is titled 'CREATE A PROJECT' and 'Step 2 / 7'. On the left is a vertical progress bar with seven steps: 1. Project type (checked), 2. Selection of collections (active, highlighted in blue with a pencil icon), 3. Project description (checked), 4. Selection of specimens (unselected), 5. Project requirements (unselected), 6. Postal address (unselected), and 7. Summary (unselected). Below the progress bar is a 'Save as draft' link. The main area is titled 'SELECT THE COLLECTIONS SETS THAT ARE RELEVANT TO YOUR PROJECT' and contains three rows of collection sets, each with a small image on the left and a checkbox on the right: 'Biological Anthropology' (checkbox unchecked), 'Biological Resources' (checkbox checked), and 'Cultural Anthropology' (checkbox unchecked). At the bottom right are 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons.

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

Impact and results achieved → Machine Annotation Service (MAS)

- A **MAS prototype for the extraction of quantitative traits** (detection of scale and computation of plant organ surface area) was implemented
- Computation service (Multi-GPU) is **deployed locally** at the Senckenberg Data and Modelling Center **and integrated into DiSSCover** as a (selectable) [Machine Annotation Service](#) (MS 3.3)

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

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▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

Machine Annotation Services Hackathon

Goals:

- **Automated Annotation of digital specimens** and their images for research use cases, digitisation, quality improvement, data enrichment

Results achieved:

- **First MAS hackathon** organised, participation from Germany, Poland, Lithuania, UK, Netherlands, Belgium and Spain, 3 new MASs created (new total: 9 MAS)

Outputs' impacts on:

- **Research use cases in plant organ detection, morphologically relevant areas in 2D specimen images, ontology based habitat term extraction with LLMs**

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

Impact and results achieved → DiSSCo Data Management Plan (D3.3)

- Key objective: **Update the provisional DiSSCo DMPs** published during ICEDIG and later supplemented by the DiSSCo Prepare (introducing maDMPs)
- **Provide Reference implementation** of the RDA DMP Common Standard **on the PlutoF platform**
 - Implemented **direct publishing of DMPs via DataCite**
 - Workshop on the [DiSSCo DMP and Standards for Taxon Hypotheses](#) in Tartu (Jan 21-22 2025)
 -

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

Next steps until the constitution of DiSSCo ERIC (next ~12 months)

- **Develop onboarding procedures** and onboard first collection-derived data and MAS services
- **Address end-user demands** (DTP workshop on DiSSCo core technical infrastructure, MS10)
- Prepare **negotiations with identified potential core service providers** (SP/GFA)
- Further **develop ELViS towards a MVP** and multi-institutional capabilities,
- **Promote adoption of DOIs** as essential added value services

User demands implementation status

- tools for data discovery (searchAdvancedFunctionality)
 - + largely already covered
 - - data to trace the origin, movement and history of specimens
 - - supporting documentation and images
- linking to external data (data:integration)
 - + support for linking implemented
 - - integration of specimen DOIs in other infrastructures
- tools:reportingStatistics: Most user stories are on collection level
- recordlevelMetadata: covered
- tools:annotation
 - + annotations implemented
 - - passing on the annotations to the institutions/CMS systems
- 2D images:
 - + supported
 - - finding trait information
 - - high quality images for type specimens

▶▶▶ Technical dimension WP3

(Longer-term) Recommendations for DiSSCo ERIC (cfr. CMP)

- Establish a **good inventory of the collections** (e.g. species level estimations) to improve access and support digitization and management plans
- **Promote large-scale (low-res) imaging and MASs** to speed up digitisation
- Develop a roadmap towards **having digital specimen DOIs for all specimens in the world**
- Develop **national infrastructures for digital media to support AI model training**
- Develop the **scientific and technologic unique features: traceability** back to the physical specimen **enables the integration of resampling and re-measuring of the specific physical object** into the research process

Technical dimension WP3

Acknowledgements

DTP WP3/WP4 6 openDS breakout group (and co-authors of MS/D):

Laurence Livermore, Matt Woodburn, Mathias Dillen, Sharif Islam, Ben Scott, Jonas Grieb, Sam Leeflang, Soulaine Theocharides, Kessy Abarenkov, Gaël Lymer, Rajapreethi Rajendran, Maxime Griveau, Daniel Bauer, Lissa Breugelmans, Maarten Trekels, Laura Tilley, Tom Dijkema, Jack Hollister, Urmaz Kõljalg, Katherine Worley

Technical dimension WP4

Technical dimension WP4

Objectives

1. Report on the state of standards interoperability and undertake a gap analysis for the next stage of DiSSCo RI development and support continued development and adoption of new community standards (Task 4.1)
2. Write and evaluate documentation for DiSSCo's operational services and related standards, and report the use of pilot DiSSCo infrastructure and the adoption of contemporary practices following workshops and community consultation (Task 4.2).

Closing of the project

Vânia Ferreira (WP5)

Completion of work packages

Finalising milestones and deliverables

End of the project: 31 May 2025

April and May to complete all work packages according to the description of the action (GA):

- ★ Good communication and collaboration are key for the delivery of the remaining project outputs
- ★ Planned internal quality review needs to be accounted for
- ★ DOI for deliverables (Open science practices in the GA)

WP1: MS1; D1.1; D1.2; MS8, MS9, D1.3

WP2: D2.1, D2.2

WP3: D3.1, D3.2; MS17

WP4: D4.1, D4.2

WP5: D5.3, D5.4

Reporting

One reporting period for the 18 months

Technical report due 2 months after the end date, i.e. by **31st July 2025**.
All WP leaders will coordinate contributions, with the support of Coordination.

The technical report should focus on the completion of work packages (the report must explain and justify the level of completion): Work done by each Partner (organisation level, not individual level) must be clearly described in the report and project outputs. This is the sole means of proof that the work described in the DoA has been delivered, thus justifying the funding of the eligible lump sum contribution(s) to the Beneficiaries.

Reporting

F&T Portal

Researchers involved in the project

Each Partner must confirm the details including:

- Contract duration
- Latest degree before entering project - Degree | Year awarded | Country
- Last professional position (if any) before entering project - Career stage | Country
- Professional position for staff members leaving the project - Career stage | Country

Failing to provide the required information will block the reporting.

Publications & Communication and Dissemination activities & Exploitation (Results)

Impact

Assessment by the Granting Authority

- **Assessment of the project** performed by the Project Officer and an independent project monitor/expert: Compliance with the description of the action and status/completion of the work packages. **No review meeting.**
- The only financial report of the project will be generated automatically by the system (F&T portal) based on the declaration of completed work packages. The payment of the balance pays the remaining lump sum shares for the implementation of the action.

DiSSCo Ri

TRANSITION

Seamless transition

**Construction
Phase**

Roundtable with the DiSSCo National Nodes

Ana Casino

The National Nodes perspective

A roundtable on the NN perspectives

Participant NNs:

- BE: Serge Scory
- UK: Alan Paton
- DK: Kim Steenstrup Pedersen
- FR: François Dusoulier
- NL: Niels Raes

The National Nodes perspective

Questions:

1. **What makes your National Node unique?**

A brief reflection on the specificities around your NN and how it might differ from the others

2. **Moving on to the Construction Phase, what crucial components will need to be addressed in preparation for joining the DiSSCo ERIC, taking into consideration these dimensions:**

- Technical
- Organisational
- Financial
- Data
- Scientific

Next steps and closing of the event

Dimitris Koureas

- ▶▶▶ ERIC Step 1 submitted
- ▶▶▶ Key ERIC docs incl. Policies drafted
- ▶▶▶ DiSSCover & ELViS core services - MVP ready
- ▶▶▶ Fundamental data standards in place

DiSSCo Ri

TRANSITION

DiSSCo Transition Project
Wrap-up event - April 1st 2025

